

PRINCIPLES OF SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITY IN TEACHER'S ACTIVITY

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Abstract. *This article provides information on the principles of spiritual and educational activity and explains its role in the development of the student's personality. Also, some directions of organizing spiritual and educational activities in higher educational institutions are explained.*

Keywords: *educational reform, personality, education, upbringing, development, information, democratic society, spirituality, enlightenment, activity, principle, creativity, initiative, values, higher education institution.*

In the conditions of the education reform taking place in our republic, it is of the utmost importance to educate a mature generation of people who are mature in all respects, who are loyal to their country, people, motherland, nation, and parents. In the updated state system, the content, goals and tasks of education will also be updated. This update is distinguished by the fact that education is built on the principle of humanism and democracy. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M.Mirziyoev, stated, "education is the most important and priority issue of every country and society, which solves not only today, but also tomorrow." Therefore, great attention is being paid to this issue at the state level in our country" [1, 353]. In fact, today it is more important than ever to organize the quality of the education and training process.

The principle of humanization and democratization of education serves as a program to ensure the development of creative activity and independence of students, teachers - educators, and their cooperation in the implementation of various socially useful works.

Spiritual and educational activities carried out in higher educational institutions have a special place in order to form creative activity, intellectual intelligence, moral potential, scientific worldview in students and young people, and to form their active participation in comprehensive social and useful work.

Accordingly, in this article, we will reflect on the principles and forms of spiritual and educational activity in educational institutions, its planning and organization.

Love for one's country, the Motherland, humane feelings are an ancient characteristic that is ingrained in the blood of our people. It is necessary to preserve and further improve these unique human qualities, to educate our children as worthy sons and daughters of a free and democratic Uzbekistan, which should be the main direction of our work in the field of spirituality. Based on this, it is necessary to clearly plan spiritual and educational activities in educational institutions, to create a system of spiritual and educational education, to focus its forms and methods on the formation of the spiritual and educational outlook of the young generation. Any education, event, set of spiritual

and educational activities will be targeted only if certain rules and requirements are followed, that is, if they are based on them. These rules, requirements, foundations are called "principles" in the science of pedagogy.

In fact, spiritual and educational activity also follows certain principles. The principles of spiritual and educational activity are the rules that express the adherence to the main requirements for the direction, content, methods and organizational forms of educational activities organized in educational institutions for the purpose of raising a mature generation, as well as for the mutual relations of the participants of the educational process.

The principles of spiritual and educational activity are a set of requirements and rules that guide teachers-educators. Therefore, adherence to these principles in the process of spiritual and educational activity increases its efficiency and develops the quality indicator.

Based on modern world and national pedagogic theories, the principles of spiritual and educational activity can be grouped as follows:

- social direction of spiritual-educational activity principle;
- the principle of free will, independence, play and romance;
- creativity, initiative, striving for innovation at work principle of approach;
- the principle of ensuring that spiritual-educational activities are planned and events are suitable for the strength of students;
- the principle of regularity, continuity, coherence and effectiveness of spiritual-educational activity;
- the principle of taking into account the age and individual characteristics of students in the organization of spiritual and educational activities.

Now we will describe the principles of this spiritual and educational activity:

1. The principle of social orientation of spiritual and educational activity. This principle is based on the organization and implementation of spiritual and educational activities, based on the ideological-political, socio-economic and spiritual-cultural development of the country, the content of activities organized outside the classroom and auditorium, the activities of clubs, associations, and the development of the country, also implies the basis of science, technology, culture, art achievements.

2. The principle of voluntary participation in spiritual and educational activities. This principle applies to the spiritual and educational activities organized in educational institutions, such as electives, circles, various sections, clubs, etc. It is focused on choosing the students based on their interest, desire, ability and their voluntariness. The principle of voluntariness, taking into account the voluntariness of the students, in order not to tire them and not strain them, also implies taking into account no more than two extracurricular activities organized in educational institutions.

3. The principle of taking into account the independence, initiative, and creativity of students-young people in spiritual and educational activities. This principle implies the need to organize spiritual and educational activities based on students' interests and initiatives. Any activity should be based on the independence of students, and the teacher-educator should inspire them and develop their activities. Then initiative, interests, and creative abilities develop in students. They learn to independently perform any event with interest and initiative in a high spirit. They develop a sense of self-control.

4. The principle of educational activities being in the form of play activities, romance. It is appropriate to apply this principle mainly to primary and secondary school students. Because children of primary and secondary school age have a greater need for play activities. But the spiritual-educational activity organized in these educational institutions is focused on the rules that express the main requirements for the direction, content, methods, organizational forms of education, and the mutual relations of the participants of the education process.

5. The principle of taking into account the age and individual characteristics of students in spiritual - educational activities. According to this principle, the tasks and contents of the events should be suitable for the age and level of preparation of the students, and they should not have a negative impact on their health, worldview, spiritual and moral potential, and intellectual intelligence.

To the listed principles of spiritual and educational activity if they are justified, attention is paid to their integrity, mutual cooperation, and complementarity, and if they are used effectively, the educational, educational and developmental activities of students will be put on the target path, and the formation of a well-rounded person as a complete person is guaranteed.

Purposeful organization and orientation of spiritual-educational activities means defining and developing its content. If there is a mismatch between the content and the plan, the intended goal will not be achieved. Accordingly, a person is brought up incorrectly, and society, people, and the person himself suffer from this. Therefore, it is necessary to clearly define the content and properly plan it. Otherwise, as the great thinker Bedil said, if the architect does not lay the first brick correctly, the wall will remain crooked even if it is made to the stars. This opinion of Bedil is related to spiritual and educational activities. As long as this is the case, it is necessary to clearly imagine the content of spiritual and educational activity, to correctly define and plan its directions.

Spiritual and educational activities represent the essence of a person as a socio-cultural being, enrich his inner world, encourage him to spiritual purification and rise, strengthen his conscience, faith, belief, worldview, ideological competence, knowledge and promotion of universal human values, or in accordance with the goals and objectives of a particular society. It is the process of formation and development of intellectual intelligence and spiritual and moral potential. Accordingly, it is necessary to define and plan the content of the spiritual and educational activities conducted in higher educational institutions in the following directions in the social, political, economic and cultural development of society.

- I. Organizational and educational works
- II. Ideological (Ideological-political) education to strengthen students' social activity and attitude to study.
- III. Forming the foundations of a scientific outlook, deepening and expanding knowledge, increasing cognitive activity.
- IV. Cultivation of universal, national morality and moral culture.
- V. Beauty, sophistication and artistic education.
- VI. Education of hard work and love for working people.
- VII. Economic and environmental education and nature protection
- VIII. Increasing the legal knowledge of young people.
- IX. Health and physical fitness of students to take care of.
- X. Spiritual-educational and ideological activities conducted with teachers-educators and employees of higher education institutions.
- XI. Working with parents and the community.

XII. Spiritual and educational activities carried out with public organizations (Youth Union, Trade Union, Women's Committee) in HEIs.

As mentioned above, in the process of teaching all subjects in higher education institutions, it is necessary to focus on increasing the spiritual and educational culture of students and on extracurricular activities. In this, every student should understand the basic meaning of the concepts of "spirituality", "culture", be aware of the roots and sources of our national spirituality, and acquire the skills of learning and learning independently from these sources. In our opinion, it is appropriate if the directions of spiritual and educational activities organized in higher education institutions are covered as follows:

Direction I: - celebration of independence, knowledge holiday, holidays related to jubilee dates, teachers' and coaches' day, Constitution Day, Defender of the Fatherland Day, religious holidays (Ramadan and Kurban holidays), Harvest holiday, Navruz holiday, Day of Remembrance and Appreciation it is planned to hold events on celebrating, organizing excursions to historical monuments, republican shrines, and holding such contests as coach of the year.

Direction II: - ideological education, taking into account the age and individual characteristics of students, learning about the internal and external policies of our country, reading and studying the works of our President, getting acquainted with the decisions and information of the Supreme Assembly, learning about the essence of the symbols of our country, and getting acquainted with the activities of statesmen. .

Direction: - intellectual work culture, cognitive activity and conscious attitude to study, educating the basics of scientific outlook. "Learn to read", "My interesting activity", "My interests", "Human and technical world", "From the life of famous people", "My dreams and interests", "The world I know and don't know", "For the development of science" conducting conversations, debates, scientific and practical conferences on topics, organizing "Think, search, find", "Fun and clever" games, etc.

Direction IV: - educational issues in Islam, which form the foundations of universal morality, studying the teachings of our scholars, "Ethical lessons", "Spirituality and life", "Life and organizing roundtable discussions on such topics as "life etiquette",

Discussions on the topics "Chastity of girls", "Pride of boyhood", "Women's culture". discussion, speech, dress, manners conversations, holding parties, conferences.

Direction V: - in order to develop the aesthetic culture of students and professors, to provide information about well-known artists, organize meetings, talk on the topics of "Music is my life", "Words take care of the heart, clothes are good", "My world - my world - Bukharai Sharif". ", publishing stands entitled "Why I love Uzbekistan", organizing meetings with creators, poets, writers, composers, actors, directors, organizing book readers' conferences: organizing art circles, going on excursions, beauty of manners, culture of behavior, taste and conducting code of conduct examination contests.

Direction VI: - with labor pioneers, heroes, and veterans organization of meetings: socially useful labor Saturdays, participation in Sundays: technical creative circles, clubs, participation in the work of repair and construction teams: "Value labor", Release of "Profession and Labor" and "Kasbim-fahrim" stands: professions, labor showcases of heroes, "Our city in the years of independence" release photomontage, etc.

Direction VII: - economic education and nature protection:

providing information about economic knowledge, savings: holding conversations about preserving classroom equipment, textbooks, study guides: organizing "Economics and Education", "Water Environment - Life" stands: meetings with economists, accountants, bank employees, question-and-answer nights organize

Direction VIII: - on increasing the legal knowledge of students and young people: raising high citizenship qualities in students and young people, cultivating feelings of respect for the constitution and laws of the independent Republic: forming loyalty to the ideals of national independence, tolerance to religious extremism and fundamentalism: people's deputies, protection of rights organization of interviews, meetings, question-and-answer evenings with the employees of the authorities: "Protect your own home", "The police is my guard", "Legal awareness - the need of the times", organization of exhibition stands: traffic rules, organization of the "Young Lawyer" circle : "Do you know the law?" conducting a screening test.

Direction IX: - care for health and physical fitness of students. Organization of morning fitness classes in educational institutions: physical education and physical culture lessons, improving the activities of clubs: increasing attention to training of the movement organs of students: organization of sports sections: development of schedules of sports games and competitions held during the academic year: "Little Universiade", Regular holding of sports games such as "Olympic Reserves", wide promotion of healthy lifestyle and its active implementation: Holding of "Healthy Body, Healthy Mind" competition.

Direction X: - spiritual-educational activities conducted between teachers-educators and students-young people. Arranging discussions and evenings on the topics of "Spirituality - the torch of the nation", "Islamic spirituality torch", "Hadith science - science of life", "Ancestors of our spirituality", "Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan", "Labor laws", "Family Code", "Criminal Code" ", "Education Law", "National Personnel Training Program" and conducting study hours of laws and regulatory documents, organizing evenings on the topics of "Teacher's Honor", "Educator's Skills", "Professional Culture", "Young Generation Mentor".

Direction XI: - work with parents and neighborhood. In order to determine the pedagogical information of the parents of students and young people in the territory of the educational institution, organization of "Spiritual-educational" knowledge screening contests: discussion, evenings on the topic "Seven neighborhood parents for one child": implementation of class, group parent meetings: Holding the "Open Day" event: organizing the activities of the parents' committee: organizing the "Parents' Corner", "Family and Society" seminars: organizing events for students and youth, holidays with parents, watching movies, going to theaters Organization of "Prosperous Mahalla", "Neighborhood - Cultural Center", "Responsible Family" meetings, parties and transfer

Direction XII: - spiritual and educational activities conducted by the higher educational institution with public organizations. Establishing activities in cooperation with public organizations such as youth union, trade union, women's committee, organizing scientific, technical, cultural, sports and physical culture associations of public organizations. Establishing pedagogical leadership over the spiritual and educational work of students after the lesson. The mentioned spiritual-educational activities are planned during the academic year. Based on the annual plan, monthly and weekly managed tasks are created.

In order to carry out spiritual and educational activities in the above-mentioned directions, work is planned and planned for the academic year or the beginning of the year.

Spiritual and educational activities are organized in different forms. It can be roughly divided into three groups:

Individual cases.

Circle work.

Public affairs.

Individual spiritual and educational activities include Olympiads, contests with talented students, contests, and exhibitions. Although many people participate in this type of event, we call it a single form of spiritual-educational activity, since each participant participates individually, defends the educational institution, region in a certain type of event. Science Olympiads are the most important means of developing interest in knowledge. Its educational value is that, although it is conducted in a certain subject, the individual tasks and questions created in it serve to develop the student's creative thinking and strengthen the desire to learn.

The type of individual spiritual-educational activity in the form of competition and exhibition also develops creativity and goal-seeking in students. For example: a student participates in contests and exhibitions such as "Skilled hands", "Technical creativity", "Poetry place", and each of them demonstrates their creativity, ability and talent. Due to the fact that these contests are held at the level of the republic starting from the higher education institution, the students develop feelings of responsibility, pride, and struggle for honor.

Nowadays, the most common form of spiritual and educational activity in educational institutions is circle work. Science circles, art amateurs, photo, radio, film amateur circles, clubs and clubs such as "Young Literary Scholar", "Young Reader", "Young Pedagogue" in higher educational institutions are also of great educational value.

Participating in circles and clubs helps students and young people to develop their cognitive abilities and creative thinking, while strengthening their responsibility towards the country, the Motherland, and the people, and therefore, it also serves to increase the spiritual and educational potential of the young generation.

Another form of spiritual and educational activity is public events. This includes matinees, theme nights, debates, question and answer nights, conferences, festivals, sports festivals and games, excursions, etc. Thus, spiritual and educational activity is comprehensive. After all, spirituality and enlightenment are the highest values. It reflects the traditions of our people, the meaningful teachings of our thinkers, the life path of our historical national heroes, and the hard life pages of those who fought for independence and freedom. That is why it is the highest value. It fulfills the great goal of educating a perfect human being according to its directions. If we implement the above-mentioned ideas and actions, the foundation stone will be laid for the formation of a perfect generation, whose spiritual and educational activity has reached its limit. For this, it is necessary to always search and act. It is necessary to make maximum use of all opportunities in this regard in spiritual and educational activities.

Thus, the spiritual and educational activities organized in educational institutions increase students' thirst for knowledge, develop their intellectual abilities and intelligence, and create a basis for their moral education.

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